

Name: _____ Age: _____

Gender: female male

Date: _____

Height: _____

Weight: _____

We would like to know how much caffeine you consume

Indicate in the table, how much you drank yesterday.

Put a line in the box for every cup/glass.

If you didn't drink the item, leave the box empty.

Portion sizes:

Small cup 150 mL	Large cup 250 mL	Small glass 150 mL	Large glass 250 mL	Energy Drink Dose 250 mL	Energy drink Dose 500 mL	Energy shot Dose 60 mL	Espresso cup 60 mL	Chocolate bar 20g

For example, like this:

	Coffee		Cola, fizzy, soft drink		Chocolate
Breakfast	II			I	I

	Coffee		Decaffeinated coffee		Espresso	Black-, green, white, mate tea		Cocoa drink		Iced tea, drinks with tea extract		Cola, mixed cola beverages (but not orangeade and lemonade)		Energy drink		Energy shot	Alcopops with energy drink, cola or coffee		Chocolate
Breakfast																			
Between breakfast and lunch																			
lunch																			
Between lunch and dinner																			
Dinner																			
After dinner																			